

SHORT NOTICE ASSESSMENTS: HOW TO SURVIVE THE JUMP FROM HEALTHCARE'S BURNING PLATFORM

In his 1993 book, *Managing at the Speed of Change*, Daryl Connor wrote about the 1988 North Sea Piper Alpha oil rig fire - a fatal explosion of an oil drilling platform in which one survivor had to choose to jump into a sea of burning oil rather than burn on the platform. He coined the term "burning platform" as a metaphor to explain the necessity of change despite the fear of the unknown consequences.

This metaphor is still used widely today in change management to describe a situation in which significant change is necessary because continuing to operate as usual is no longer an option. For healthcare, this metaphor aligns nicely to describe the introduction of short-notice assessments; the implementation of which constitutes a very different focus to standard practice that can't be resolved by doing "more of the same".

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WHY THE CHANGE? A RECAP ON HOSPITAL ACCREDITATION IN AUSTRALIA

Hospital accreditation is not a new concept and has evolved over time based on our hospital system's needs, with the most recent significant changes occurring with the establishment of the Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Healthcare (The Commission) in 2006.

Since its establishment, the Commission has been working towards accreditation reforms to improve safety and quality outcomes for patients. This activity has resulted in the development of a set of national safety and quality health service standards for use in an Australian Health Service Safety and Quality Accreditation (AHSSQA) Scheme. These National Safety and Quality Health Service (NSQHS) Standards were submitted to the Australian Health Ministers' Council (AHMC) and were approved in September 2011.¹

The national accreditation scheme ran on a 3-4 year cycle and was intended to reduce the complexity and

resource-intensive nature of accreditation through the alignment of a common set of standards. Hospitals were encouraged to embed these standards within their organisations to ensure safe, quality care every day - not just at accreditation time.

In reality, health services adopted a flurry of activity that aligned with the accreditation cycle, whereby the entire organisation embarked on a huge amount of stressful, resource hungry activities to ensure everything was up to date and in line with standards. It was evident that this 3-4 year accreditation cycle was creating a one-off event, rather than encouraging the standards to be embedded into ongoing care practices. In an effort to disrupt this cyclical practice the Commission, from January 2019 to 1 July 2023, introduced a voluntary short notice assessment scheme.² Once reviewed, and as of July 2023, short notice assessments have become mandatory practice whereby hospitals and day procedure centres (collectively known as health service organisations (HSOs)) undergo real time assessments that can occur at any point during a three-year cycle.

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1 Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Healthcare, <https://www.safetyandquality.gov.au/sites/default/files/migrated/Development-of-the-National-Safety-and-Quality-Health-Service-Standards.pdf>

2 Australian Commission on Safety and Quality in Healthcare, <https://www.safetyandquality.gov.au/standards/nsqhs-standards/assessment-nsqhs-standards/short-notice-assessment>

A SIGNIFICANT CHANGE OPPORTUNITY FOR HSOS TO EMBRACE - ARE YOU READY?

The implementation of short-notice assessments has created a burning platform for HSOs; while the resource-hungry accreditation process may have worked on a 3-4 year accreditation cycle, these past approaches are no longer fit for purpose and cannot be scaled to a level of activity that will satisfy a short notice period.

This is an opportunity for HSOs to turn their risks in to inspired clinical practice:

POOR PATIENT OUTCOMES TO RICH PATIENT OUTCOMES

When hospitals draw resources away from patients to pass accreditation, the likelihood of suboptimal patient experiences and adverse events increases. To defocus between accreditation events does not provide consistently good patient outcomes. Implementation of good clinical governance systems changes the focus from a cyclical focus to best practice every day.

LOW STAFF MORALE AND TURNOVER TO ENGAGED AND HAPPY HEALTHCARE STAFF

In an already stretched and burnt-out workforce, a poor approach (or no approach) to accreditation is a stressful and demanding process for hospital staff. Inefficiency can exacerbate stress and reduce morale, potentially leading to increased turnover, burnout, and decreased job satisfaction. Long term, the organisational culture will suffer, with the work becoming about satisfying accreditation rather than providing the best care. Optimisation of a good clinical governance system provides managers and staff the support to create consistently good care and good job satisfaction.

NOT PASSING ACCREDITATION TO BEING ACCREDITATION READY EVERYDAY

Hospitals that fail to meet accreditation standards may face legal and financial repercussions. They could be at risk of losing accreditation status, which can affect their eligibility for reimbursement by insurance providers and Medicare. Legal liabilities may also arise from incidents related to non-compliance. Worst of all, poor systems commonly align with poor patient outcomes. Good clinical governance systems ensure that HSOs are not engaging in activities without purpose. Alignment between strategic purpose and point of care is integral to achieving meaningful point of care purpose and results.

MISSED OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVEMENT TO MOVING YOUR ORGANISATION FROM GOOD TO GREAT

The accreditation process provides hospitals with an opportunity to assess their operations and make necessary improvements. Inefficient preparation may cause hospitals to miss out on these opportunities, hindering their ability to grow and evolve. By having the right dynamic leadership and clinical governance systems in place, it allows the organisation to not only be 'everyday ready' but to adopt a conscious choice to be best it can be.

HOW DO I MOVE BEYOND COMPLIANCE?

To satisfy the requirements of short notice assessments, many organisations will need to fundamentally change their approach to accreditation; they must work towards being “accreditation-ready” every day and develop a more sophisticated, whole-of-organisation approach to accreditation. To achieve this, organisations need to consider and examine two key areas:

1. Clinical Governance - ensuring you have a robust system
2. Organisational culture - reframing how we think about accreditation

CLINICAL GOVERNANCE - ENSURING YOU HAVE A ROBUST SYSTEM

A robust clinical governance framework serves as the backbone of a healthcare organisation's ability to maintain compliance with accreditation and regulatory standards, including during short-notice assessments - but it does far more than that. A good clinical governance framework, that is aligned with the organisation's vision and purpose, promotes a consistent culture of accountability, risk management, and continuous improvement, all of which are crucial for readiness and success when faced with unannounced evaluations or assessments.

But what makes a framework robust? An organisation's framework may be written by experts, cover all the right areas and align perfectly with the standards, but is it used and referred to beyond the people who created it? While nearly all health organisations have a clinical governance framework, many would concede that a true understanding and enactment of this framework is not present on the frontline.

Organisations must understand that their clinical governance framework will greatly support the transition to short-notice accreditation, but only if it is 'lived and breathed' on the frontline.

ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE - REFRAMING HOW WE THINK ABOUT ACCREDITATION

Accreditation is sometimes seen as the “gold standard” of care, with organisations taking comfort from just being accredited. HSOs need to move beyond this mentality if they want to be accreditation-ready every day. Accreditation and compliance is still important, but we need to shift the emphasis from quality control to quality improvement. Compliance still needs to be embedded in the organisation's systems, processes and culture, but understanding improvement science and what 'consumer centred' really means, is the key to the 'value-add' in achieving excellence in care outcomes.

Before any change can take place at a process level, organisations must first understand that the culture around accreditation must change; rather than being thought of as the gold standard of care, staff must understand that being accreditation-ready all the time is the minimum standard of care that is expected. Creating meaning for staff is the first step to engagement, 'People support what they help to create'.³

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³ Four Clinical Governance Rabbit Holes to Avoid (2023) Australasian Institute of Clinical Governance

WHAT DOES IT LOOK LIKE TO ADDRESS THESE NEEDS?

To change culture and effectively embed a clinical governance framework, organisations will need to: support change management and develop culture through a clear purpose, embed that purpose into their clinical governance framework and build clinical governance capability through all levels of the organisation.

SUPPORT CHANGE MANAGEMENT AND DEVELOP CULTURE AND LEADERSHIP THROUGH A CLEAR PURPOSE

Identify the purposeful 'flag' on the hill

For organisations to move beyond seeing accreditation as the gold standard of care, they must first identify what the gold standard should be, and then clearly and simply articulate it. A shared purpose can be, in itself, an invisible leader.⁴

Enable clinical leaders at all levels and avoid "trickle-down" clinical governance

All organisations are already a mix of formal and informal leadership, whether we recognise it or not. The decisions and actions staff take every day create the care your organisation provides. Change happens, not only through senior leaders and middle managers but also through informal opinion leaders and champions at other levels. However, a resistant or stagnant organisational culture can pose a significant barrier to leadership.

When leaders across the organisation are supported to work within a common definition and framework, their shared leadership actions can aggregate, stretching across team and departmental boundaries for organisation-wide impact.⁵

EMBED YOUR PURPOSE INTO YOUR CLINICAL GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK

Once organisations identify their 'flag' on the hill, the best way to embed this goal into the culture of the organisation is to build it into the clinical governance framework.

Adjunct Professor Shane Crowe, Executive Director, Nursing & Midwifery reflects on how Western Health was able to shift the process of accreditation from burdensome and compliance-focused to having clear, non-negotiable expectations by embedding the framework into the culture of the organisation. The framework "works well because it resonates with the staff, it's simple to understand and it's less around compliance and more around what we're trying to achieve as a healthcare organisation". As part of the review of systems and processes, Shane and his team reviewed the way the framework was operationalised and where necessary tweaked elements to ensure that there were no gaps and that it was meeting the needs of the growing health service.⁶

BUILD CLINICAL GOVERNANCE CAPABILITY THROUGHOUT ALL LEVELS OF YOUR ORGANISATION TO BRING THE FRAMEWORK TO LIFE

Often, clinical governance expertise and accountability is siloed with the quality team. Clinical governance is everybody's responsibility, regardless of whether you're a clinician, a board member or a cleaner. Therefore, hospitals must build clinical governance capability through all levels of the organisation through education so that everyone in the organisation is curious about problems, confident enough to speak up about them and committed enough to follow through with solving them.

4 Hickman, G. R., & Sorenson, G. J. (2014) The power of invisible leadership: How a compelling common purpose inspires exceptional leadership. SAGE Publications, Inc. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781506335421>

5 Australasian Institute of Clinical Governance (AICG). (2023). Everyday Clinical Leadership: A Foundation for Successful Clinical Governance. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8424365>

6 Australasian Institute of Clinical Governance (AICG). (2023). Investing in People and Systems - Western Health's Clinical Governance Philosophy. <https://www.aicg.edu.au/resources/investing-in-people-and-systems-western-healths-clinical-governance-philosophy/>

HOSPITALS WILL BE REWARDED FOR JUMPING OFF THE BURNING PLATFORM

The benefits for hospitals undertaking the change management process of adopting an 'always on' approach to accreditation are numerous, with the greatest impacts felt by patients and staff.

HOSPITALS WILL MOVE BEYOND COMPLIANT CARE TO DELIVER EXCELLENT CARE

Shifting the focus of accreditation from a one-off event to business as usual will allow staff to move beyond compliance and pursue excellence in the care they deliver. Staff will be able to deliver safer care, and patient experiences and outcomes will improve across the entire patient journey.

Safer hospital care doesn't just reduce harm to patients, it also saves money for taxpayers and can positively impact care accessibility.⁷

YOUR WORKFORCE WILL BE PROTECTED FROM BURNOUT AND STRESS

By building accreditation processes into everyday practice, staff will avoid feeling overwhelmed or stressed when the assessor announces their intent to visit. Hospitals can avoid the flurry of activity that is usually associated with accreditation, shifting the mindset for accreditation from burdensome to business as usual. Additionally, if clinicians see accreditation as part of the patient care processes as opposed to a box-ticking exercise, staff satisfaction increases which can reduce workforce challenges such as poor performance and turnover.

"I AM RESPONSIBLE" - ALL STAFF BECOME ACCOUNTABLE FOR BUILDING A CONTINUOUS IMPROVEMENT CULTURE

The quality of clinical care is created in every encounter between consumers and staff. On the ground leaders who take accountability for good patient care are essential in achieving better patient outcomes. As we navigate the ever-evolving challenges of providing quality care across human services, a powerful tool for overcoming these challenges is for all staff to have an "I am responsible" philosophy. This will ultimately contribute to organisational performance and success.

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⁷ Grattan Institute. (2018). Safer Care Saves Money; How to Improve Patient Care and Save Public Money at the Same Time. <https://grattan.edu.au/wp-content/uploads/2018/08/Safer-care-saves-money.pdf>

Conclusion

The introduction of short-notice assessments may have created a burning platform for healthcare. Still, organisations can take comfort in knowing that by adopting an accreditation-ready mindset every day, we will see better outcomes, not just for the patient, but for our valuable health workforce.

Jump off the burning platform with the support of AICG. Contact us about team training at info@aicg.edu.au

ABOUT THE AICG

The Australasian Institute of Clinical Governance (AICG) is a division of Health Education Australia Limited (HEAL), a not-for-profit organisation that has been synonymous with quality health education for over 100 years.

The AICG was formed in direct response to an identified need for health and care professionals to strengthen their skills in clinical governance to reduce the occurrence of adverse events, and is now recognised as the leading cross-sector, interprofessional clinical governance education provider across Australia and New Zealand.

The AICG firmly believes that by building the clinical governance capability of our health and care workforce we can improve consumer safety and quality care and deliver better health outcomes for the community.

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E. info@aicg.edu.au

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